

THE ROLE OF SOCIAL PEDAGOGY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF FEELINGS OF LOVE FOR THE MOTHERLAND AND PATRIOTISM IN STUDENTS AND SCHOOLCHILDREN

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Abstract. *One of the citizenship values that plays a role in the social studies curriculum is patriotism. The purpose of the current study was to look at the patriotism perceptions of social studies instructors. The study, which was intended to be a phenomenological inquiry, involved a total of 14 social studies instructors who were chosen using the maximum variation approach. Using an interview form that was semi-structured, the study data were gathered. Using the NVivo software, the data were analyzed using a content analysis methodology. According to the study's findings, the participating social studies instructors believed themselves to be closer to blind patriotism and explained patriotism using themes of love, dedication, and duty.*

Key words. *Patriotism, civic engagement, civic education, and social studies instruction.*

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Introduction

Patriots are citizens who have learned the virtue of patriotism and are crucial to any society. This is mostly because patriotism is a political notion that emphasizes allegiance to the nation without highlighting any ethical qualities. It includes sentiments of belonging, love, pride, and caring for a country. So, patriotism serves as both a socio-psychological behavior that expresses people's commitment to their country and a political referent in the same way. Depending on how citizenship education is approached, the political and social reflections of patriotism can have either a good or negative tendency. Many connotations have been given to patriotism depending on its good and bad aspects. Patriotism is categorized both favorably and negatively based on its democratic, constructive, critical, citizen, civilian, and disobedient characteristics as well as negatively based on its blind, militaristic, authoritarian, and obedient features. Dazzling patriotism is linked to nationalism and authoritarianism. It is thought that critical thinking is used to create patriotism in the forms that are constructive. In order to enhance and change national policies, constructive patriotism has a key loyalty component. It is favorably regarded as a civic value in this regard. Blind and honorable patriotism entails devotion to and pride in one's nation.

Method

Family, schools, and the environment all play crucial roles in how well-rounded citizens become patriots. Many activities in educational programs and extracurricular activities conducted in schools teach children the virtue of patriotism in direct and indirect ways. Students should be taught patriotism, which is included in numerous courses including social sciences, Turkish, and those relating to citizenship and democracy education. These classes directly instill patriotism in

the kids, as well as indirectly through participation in national festival events. This phenomenological research study was created with the goal of examining social studies teachers' views on patriotism. Due to its inclusion in the social studies curriculum and its importance as one of the core civic virtues, patriotism is closely related to social studies lessons. Given that one of the main goals of patriotism education is to foster positive patriotic beliefs among students, the perceptions of instructors of patriotism and the notions they attach to it become crucial issues. A phenomenological design was chosen as a result. Typically, phenomenological research looks on how people interpret, understand, or temporarily apply a certain concept.

People experience, pursue, and understand patriotism via observation in their daily lives. As a result, it has an impact on daily living. The participants in the current study were chosen using the greatest diversity sampling approach. In phenomenological research, maximum diversity sampling is used to examine how people with a range of diverse characteristics interpret the phenomena. Participating in this study were a total of 14 social studies teachers, each of whom varied in terms of gender, department of graduation, degree of education (undergraduate, master of arts, or PhD), professional seniority, location of birth, age, socioeconomic status, and kind of school they teach in. 5 of them were men and 9 were women, ranging in age from 26 to 53. The instructor with the most experience was 26 years old, while the one with the least experience had only been a teacher for two years. 12 instructors worked at public schools, but only 2 in private ones. In terms of the department from which they graduated, 7 had a bachelor's degree in social studies education, while 6 instructors were history majors and 1 was a geography major. How beliefs about patriotism were diverse and how variations interacted in specific concepts were key selection factors for participants. The maximum diversity sampling approach provides a range of viewpoints on particular subjects. Patton emphasizes that while several viewpoints could appear to be restricting in terms of integrity, identifying the shared elements among them really improves the research's conclusions.

Semi-structured interviews were used to gather the research's data. Contrary to structured interviews, semistructured ones give interviewers considerable latitude in how they organize their thoughts on the subject at hand. By consulting with experts and using a test application, a semi-structured interview form was created. The concept of patriotism, the traits of a patriotic individual, their perspectives on patriotism in their everyday lives, how other people in society see patriotism, and social studies lessons with reference to patriotism were all discussed during the interviews with participating social studies instructors. The interviews typically lasted between 30 and 40 minutes.

Voice recorders were used to capture the interviews. The records were then verbatim transcribed and subjected to inductive content analysis using the qualitative data analysis software NVivo. Line by line coding of the data produced three primary themes and 23 subthemes. One-fifth of the data was independently coded by two researchers, and their results were compared to boost the analysis's trustworthiness. For ethical considerations, remarks made by the participants were explicitly cited while the findings were being presented, using the nicknames that had been given to them. The meaning of patriotism, patriotism in society, and patriotism in education were three major issues around which the research's conclusions were grouped. Teachers of social studies described patriotism in terms of the lesson, students, people, and society. In other words, teachers

used the social studies lesson, pupils, patriotic and non-patriotic people, and rules of conduct compatible and incompatible with patriotism when defining the notion of patriotism. Instructors emphasized that everyone should become aware of their own and other people's rules of behavior, which would make them more cautious, observant, and socially conscious. Participants were questioned about what the term "patriot" reminds them of, what humanitarian qualities are equal to patriotism, and how patriotism may be improved in individuals in order to understand the instructors' ideas of patriotism holistically. According to the research, teachers' definitions of patriotism include both love of the nation and patriotism. On the other side, instructors also discussed patriotism using the ideas of loyalty and duty.

Several educators emphasized that some societal behaviors do not align with patriotism. Individualization, discrimination, and marginalization are among them, as is demeaning patriotism by employing it in catchphrases. Instructors illustrated how frequently prejudice and marginalization are seen in society by using examples from their own everyday lives. These behaviors are inconsistent with the concept of patriotism and may even have a negative impact on it. Teachers contend that a lack of tolerance is the root cause of social marginalization and discrimination, since individuals are intolerant of other people, events, or values. They believe that ignorance of other cultures undermines tolerance, which leads to discrimination and marginalization. For instance, instructor Nurcan offered the following justification for her viewpoint: "Because there are so many diverse people in society.

Result

The participating instructors thought that the social studies curriculum was the best setting in which to teach the importance of patriotism, while it was not the only one. Teacher Aylin, for instance, stated that she believed there should be a wider range and that patriotism should be taught in all subjects, from reading to numeracy. Many teachers have different perspectives on teaching patriotism, including teaching tolerance, critical thinking, and scientific thinking. According to Teacher Sefa, patriotism may be taught in social studies classes by saying that one should "get a job, develop a profession, study, and discover the truth in order to work for the country and nation... You shouldn't trust the rumors in order to find out the truth. Several of the lecturers emphasized the fact that today's youth lack a feeling of patriotism and are not as engaged in it as they were as students. Instructors believe that pupils' patriotism is insufficient for a variety of reasons. While some instructors mention the impact of technology advancements in lowering the children's consciousness of nationality, others claim that the knowledge of respect and tolerance in society has a negative impact on children's feeling of patriotism. For instance, Elif stated that "Today's kids live in a radically different environment. Despite our best efforts, students are constantly distracted by outside influences when they are out and about, which causes them to forget what they have learned in class. Teachers said that kids' views and behaviors about the worth of patriotism are influenced by their parents' approach to patriotism. For instance, teacher Nurcan stated, "I believe that the parents are what really important. These kids don't read or do research. They are young and ignorant of many things... I think their animated behavior is a result of what they observe or hear in their household. Similar to what the student stated, the instructor said, "Ah, well, actually there are components of it as you know: environment, family, and school. In actuality, the family should be in charge of the child's education initially. Something that parents

can use for a long period should be offered. Teachers of social studies who took part in the lesson used words like love, devotion, and duty to describe patriotism. The greatest show of patriotism, according to these educators, is love and allegiance for the nation. They discussed this in terms of historical awareness, a shared culture, independence, and territorial integrity. Teachers described patriots in this regard as those who "perform their work the best" and "have the sense of 'us. The same goes for performing one's duties "honestly and faithfully," which is a sign of patriotism. These findings suggested that some of the participating social studies educators may exhibit blind patriotism.

Conclusion

These findings suggest that participating teachers' sentiments of patriotism are incompatible with active and democratic citizenship and are more akin to blind patriotism. In order to provide their students with a positive active and democratic citizenship education as well as the necessary constructive patriotism education in the social studies lessons, it can therefore be said that both preservice and inservice teachers should receive active and democratic citizenship education. It would be beneficial to construct in-service training programs for teachers in this context, and present teacher training programs should be improved in terms of the quality of active and democratic citizenship education delivered. Also, more thorough study may be done on how teachers, potential teachers, and teacher trainers see active citizenship and patriotism.

List of used literature

1. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/312525254>
2. <https://doi.org/10.18844/wjet.v14i3.7328>
3. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/280216992_The_Teaching_of_Patriotism_and_Human_Rights_An_uneasy_entanglement_and_the_contribution_of_critical_pedagogy
4. Westheimer, J. (2006). Politics and patriotism in education. *Phi Delta Kappan*, 87, 608-620.
5. Yazıcı, S. & Yazıcı, F. (2010). Yurtseverlik eğitimi: Tarih ve sosyal bilgiler öğretmenlerinin algı, tutum ve eğitimsel uygulamalarına yönelik bir araştırma. *Uluslararası Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 3(10), 649-660.
5. Straughn, J. B. & Andriot, A. L. (2011). Education, civic patriotism and democratic citizenship: Un packing the education effect on political involvement. *Sociological Forum*, 26(3), 556-580.